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«ROMAN-GERMAN TILSHUNOSLIGINING DOLZARB MASALALARI» XALQARO
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Xalqaro anjuman materiallaridan iborat mazkur to'plamga mutaxassislikka yo'naltirilgan chet tili ta'limining dolzarb mummolari, chet tilini o'qitishda innovatsion pedagogik texnologiyalar, fanda yaratilgan innovatsiyalar: tajriba va yutuq, tilshunoslikning dolzarb masalalari, mutaxassislik fanlarini o'qitishda xorijiy til va tarjimaning o'rni masalalariga oid maqolalar kiritilgan. Konferentsiya materiallarida soha olimlari: filologlar, adabiyotshunos va tilshunoslar, tarjimashunoslar bilan bir qatorda, shu jabhalarda ilmiy izlanishlarini olib borayotgan tadqiqotchilar, magistrantlar hamda bakalavriat bosqichi talabalarining tadqiqot natijalariga bag'ishlangan maqolalar o'rin olgan.

To'plam filologiya sohasi va nofilologik yo'nalishlarda chet tili o'qitishga qiziquvchi keng kitobxonlar va tadqiqotchilar ommasiga mo'ljallangan.

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To'plamga kiritilgan maqolalar va tezislarning mazmuni hamda sifatiga mualliflar mas'uldir.

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NATIONAL AND CULTURAL SPECIFICITY OF RELIGIOUS PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS

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Abstract: This article discusses the national and cultural features of religious phraseological units. A number of scientific papers have been studied on this topic. The views of various scientists on this concept are given as examples.

Keywords: language; religion; phraseology; religious phraseological unit; culture; national-cultural; linguoculturology; nation.

Language is the most important means of storing and transmitting information, a means of collecting and transmitting national and cultural values. Linguistic consciousness forms the national linguistic landscape of the world - a set of ideas about the world, historically formed in the mind of a certain language community, and reflected in the language. The national language is closely related to the psychology and identity of the people, and is a means of conveying its customs, patterns, habits, etc.

Different languages give a certain uniqueness and national flavor to the image of the world, which is explained by the differences in people's lifestyle, religion, culture and traditions. The worldview of people shapes the landscape of the world, and it follows that the mentality of any language community is largely determined by the landscape of the world, which represents the perception of the other by its members. One and the same concept has different means of linguistic expression in different languages. Ways and forms of thinking, as well as the formation of concepts, are determined by the uniqueness of the socio-cultural and natural features of the life of a certain language community.

The language of each nation is unique, because its "way of understanding things", the ability to understand the material world and interpret it through mental activity and language is manifested in the linguistic mind. People's self-awareness is their way of thinking and is closely related to people's lifestyle, psychology, and mentality.

According to W. Humboldt, any language has linguistic features that express the character of the nation that speaks that language. Regardless of the situation, the language of the nation, even the nation itself, does not know exactly when it appeared [1; 376].

V.V. Kolesov says that the concept of mentality is closely related to the concept of the national landscape of the world. "Mentality is a worldview in the categories and forms of the native language, which embodies the intellectual, spiritual and volitional qualities of the national character in its typical manifestations" [2; 13-24].

According to A. Ya. Gurevich, mentality is a way of seeing the world, it is not at all similar to ideology, which deals with thought systems, and in many ways the main thing is not reflected and logically defined. Folk mentality is actualized in the most important cultural concepts of the language [3; 92].

The famous cultural scientist Yu.M. Lotman in his work "Лекция по структурной поэтике" ("paragraph "Language is a material art") says that the structure of language is the result of human mental activity, and therefore the material of oral art already contains the results of its emphasized activity [4; 68]. According to A. T. Khrolenko, there is a correct opinion that language is a natural substrate of culture and is absorbed into all aspects of it. It serves as a means of regulating the world, a means of strengthening the ethnic outlook [5; 248].

In our opinion, when a person reflects culture in his speech, he also describes the world around him. Each society develops its own worldview system, which includes the understanding of the surrounding world and oneself as a part of this world. The components of this system are national concepts. National concepts reflect concepts related to a specific nation, determined by its lifestyle, history, religion, customs and traditions. These concepts find their expression in the linguistic landscape of the people and are passed from generation to generation as a systematized, national-cultural experience of perception of reality.

According to I.S. Kon, in order to understand the national character of a people, first of all, it is necessary to study its history, social structure and culture. The national stereotype of a person is unique, but it can be manifested only against the background of universal characteristics, attitudes and values system common to all nations and peoples. And this, in turn, the analysis of the world scene allows to understand how national cultures differ, how they complement each other at the level of world culture [6; 122-158].

Therefore, "the uniqueness of phraseological units is determined both by the internal laws of the language and by extralinguistic factors. The structural characteristics of phraseological units depend on the type of language and the methods of expressing grammatical relations, on the lexical structure of the nominative methods available in a certain language, on the figurativeness and semantics on the methods of expressing certain phenomena of objective reality in languages [7; 86-90].

Despite many studies on phraseology, phraseological meaning, types of phraseological units, the principles of classification of phraseological units have not yet been fully studied. Classification of phraseological units was and still is one of the urgent problems of phraseology. The national character of phraseological units is manifested in the material and spiritual conditions of the socio-economic life of the people. In this regard, V.N. Telia says: "The system of images within the phraseological unit is related to the formation of the worldview of the nation, its material, social or spiritual culture. For this reason, they provide information about the national-cultural experience, traditions, and customs of that nation" [8; 13-24].

I.G. Herder emphasized that the mentality and character of the people is related to their lifestyle, education, and political system. He believed that it is necessary to study its history, culture, most important traditions, customs and ceremonies in order to know and understand the mentality of the people [9; 274].

Another famous German philosopher G.F. Hegel focused on the fact of "rationalization" of the national mentality in the course of its cultural and historical evolution, who considered the concept of "people's spirit" equal to the concept of "people's consciousness". G.F. Hegel believed that the maturity of the people's mentality is determined by its ability to think rationally. This ability determines socio-technical development, development of science and art, a nation's place among other nations in world history, as well as the level of development of self-awareness [10; 372].

According to G.F. Hegel, the religious factor is of particular importance in the formation of public consciousness. The spirit of the people is reflected in the religion, its spiritual qualities are manifested, and the goals of the historical movement are based. For many peoples, religious belief is a "spiritual substance" in which, as a rule, the reasons for their fundamental differences are hidden in assessing the specific characteristics of the soul of people as a complex opposite unity. Using the dialectical principle of the unity and struggle of opposites, G.F. Hegel highlighted the strengths and weaknesses of the character and mentality of each nation.

In conclusion, it can be said that the concept of "national character" is actively used in modern socio-humanitarian discourse. A comprehensive study of the national character as one of the forms of re-creation of cultural codes can be the basis for the processes of preserving the identity of modern ethnic groups and their actualization in modern conditions.

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